

BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS AND PRODUCTIVE ZAKAT REVIEW

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Abstract

This study aims to map and review research on productive zakat and the extent to which this topic has been reviewed, analyzed and used as a variable in a scientific study published in a Scopus indexed journal. Using a bibliometric analysis approach and the help of the Harzing Publish or Perish search software focused on Scopus indexed publications, only four relevant articles were found related to the keywords productive; zakat in the last 10 years. One of the results of previous studies shows that the empowerment of the use of productive zakat to the community significantly reduces poverty, and allows to reduce inequality and end poverty in Indonesia and other findings show that the model of distributing productive zakat by zakat institutions in Indonesia uses two approaches, namely through direct business capital assistance and through proposals aimed at victims of natural disasters. They use zakat to start a business or develop a business that is already owned by the recipient of productive zakat funds. Therefore, this study recommends that in the next research can empirically re-analyze the use of productive zakat variables in the macro-Sharia field in more depth and can be generalized across sectors of other fields of scientific studies.

Keyword: Bibliometric Analysis, Productive Zakat Review.

Background

Zakat is one of the main sectors in the economic field of Muslim countries. As one of the third pillars of Islam, the payment of zakat is an obligation for a Muslim who is qualified to sanctify his property by distributing it to mustahiq based on certain criteria, (Arifin & Anwar, 2021; Ryandono & Nanda, 2020; Zaenal et al., 2018). The term zakat is defined as paying a certain part of the property to the entitled (mustahiq) in accordance with the provisions prescribed by Islamic law (Djaghballou et al., 2018; Widiastuti et al., 2018). According to Law Number 23 of 2011 concerning Zakat Management, zakat is defined as wealth that must be paid by a Muslim or business entity to those who are entitled according to Islamic law. In addition, the results of research by Majid, (2017) confirm that empirically the decision of Muzakki (zakat payers) to pay zakat in Baitul Mal Aceh, Indonesia is supported by the existence of zakat regulations (Qanun) and to increase awareness of the Acehnese people to fulfilling zakat still needs to be equipped with relevant knowledge about the obligation to pay zakat.

Therefore, from the various definitions of zakat, it can be concluded that the definition of zakat in general is the percentage of wealth that must be spent by a Muslim who has qualified to be handed over to the rightful. In addition to the attributes of zakat as a unique instrument in poverty alleviation, if carried out systematically and well-organized, it will be able to bring a multiplier effect that helps increase national income due to the acceleration of wealth circulation that occurs in developing countries. Economics. For example, productive zakat

given to mustahiq not to be spent directly for consumption purposes, can encourage mustahiq to manage and produce the wealth it has, (Alfaizin et al., 2018; Widiastuti et al., 2018).

Zakat has enormous potential to be developed economically. In the last decade, zakat has experienced rapid growth marked by an increase in total zakat collection funds. Because Indonesia has the largest Muslim population in the world, which is 85 percent of the total population of Indonesia or 216.66 million people, (Zaenal et al., 2018). This can also be illustrated from the increase in the collection of zakat, alms, and shadaqah funds from 2002 to 2015, (Zaenal et al., 2018). This data shows that public awareness to pay zakat through certified zakat institutions has increased. This positive trend of collecting zakat also has implications for increasing public trust in the performance of zakat institutions in managing zakat funds, (Asrori et al., 2020; Ryandono & Nanda, 2020; Zaenal et al., 2018).

Thus productive zakat will be related to various institutions and for as a form of implementation of Islamic values, carrying out economic transactions must be able to clinging to the rules created by God by the principles of God's oneness, free will, and balance. Thus, it can be avoided from the practice of usury that is forbidden by the majority of scholars. Islam in the holy book of the Qur'an and the Prophet said that the as-Sunnah had given directions on the good ordinances of the muamalah and then practiced them. In Islamic economic activities, namely zakat and waqf, especially productive ones, will bring the common good by eliminating the economic gap between society through the distribution of wealth and the Islamic economic system, the rich can help the poor to obtain capital to make trade and reduce the unemployment rate, (Hariyanto et al., 2020).

From previous studies, this study reviewed studies related to productive zakat variables. This research uses a different method from the previous research which used qualitative and quantitative method approaches, namely by using the bibliometric analysis method, which collecting and re-mapping previous research so that new research gaps can be found that are good for future research to be retested in future research. Thus the research is different in terms of research methodology when compared to the research of the last 10 years. And the results of practical and theoretical research are of course expected to be useful for enriching references related to zakat and can be used as a basis for policy making that related to the implementation of productive zakat.

Research Methods

Analisa with this bibliometric method is carried out to find articles that are hooked and relevant to the productive zakat desired by the researcher and this bibliometric analysis it is possible for researchers to analyze how often articles related to the shari'a sukuk of the study are cited, what is the average citation per year, whether it is cited jointly by other authors with data sources that can be sourced from Scopus, Web of Science (WoS) or Google Scholar. There are several reviews related to this study, penulis using access to a comprehensive database derived from Scopus, arguing that choosing Scopus lies in its availability its data base which is almost 60 percent larger than the Web of Science Databases (WoS), (Zhao & Strotmann, 2015). Therefore, the author searched for relevant articles and journals for this

study from the Scopus database with the following keywords; "productive; zakat" and s tudi this limits its analysis only to the discipline of "accounting" which emphasizes only on the variable "productive zakat".

Results and Discussion

In this section of the results and discussion, the results of the analysis using bibliometric analysis techniques are described. First, this section will present the results of the analysis in the form of citations, followed sequentially with a co-citation analysis of the keyword "productive; zakat". There are items to review in the analysis of these citations, such as the number of publications per year, the most cited per document; the most dominant authors; the most dominant journals; the most dominant institutions, and the most dominant countries. The following table presents search results with Harzing Publish or Perish software.

Table 1. Resume Results of Previous Research on Productive Zakat

Summary	
Criterion	Sum
Book Chapter	3
Article	18
Citations	37
Conferece Paper	7
Source	Scopus
Country	
Author	26
Number of references in the last 10 years (2012-2022)	4

It can be seen in the table of research trends related to "productive; zakat" only published 18 articles indexed in Scopus, researched only in two countries with four different authors. And in terms of time period if revisited based on the number of citations, then the highest was in 2018 and 2020 with six citations and the second most in the year 2014 and 2015 with five citations, as presented in the following diagram.

Figure 1. Number of Citations in 2014-2020

As already presented in figure 1, and when combined with table 2 it can be seen that the most citations of a total of six citations were written by Hariyanto et al., (2020) and Widiastuti et al., (2018), with the sub-fields of research studied in the field of Islamic accounting specifically, consider table 2 below.

Table 2: Number of Citations, Penulis and Title

Quotation	Author	Heading
6	(Hariyanto et al., 2020)	Effectiveness of the economic system to Zakat and Waqf for empowerment of the Ummah in Indonesia
6	(Widiastuti et al., 2018)	Optimization of Zakat fund management in regional Zakat institution
5	(Njoto-Feinard, 2014)	Financing Muhammadiyah: Early economic endeavours of a Muslim modernist mass organization in Indonesia (1920s-1960s)
5	(Baidhawiy, 2015)	Lazismu and remaking the Muhammadiyah's new way of philanthropy
2	(Mohsin et al., 2021)	Measuring the Performance of Poverty Reduction Programs in Rural Pakistan
2	(Widiastuti et al., 2021)	A mediating effect of business growth on zakat empowerment program and mustahiq's welfare
2	(Grace & Nurzaman, 2019)	Assesment of zakat distribution: A case study on zakat community development in Bringinsari village, Sukorejo district, Kendal
2	(Zaenal et al., 2018)	Increasing urban community empowerment through changing of poverty rate index on the productive zakat impact
1	(Ryandono & Nanda, 2020)	The transformation of mustahiq as productive zakat recipients in Surabaya

1	(Calder, 2017)	Zakāt in imāmī shī‘ī jurisprudence, from the tenth to the sixteenth century A.D
1	(Gantira Mira et al., 2020)	ERP system implementation with accounting modules in national amil zakat institutions
1	(Rini et al., 2020)	Zakat and poverty: An Indonesian experience
1	(Sumai et al., 2019)	Role of zakat in poverty reduction and food security
1	(Adnan et al., 2019)	The potential for implementing micro financing from the zakat fund in Malaysia
1	(Princess et al., 2019)	The Mustahiq empowerment model: A collaboration between Sharia Bank and OPZ in optimizing zakat funds

Furthermore, the following table 3 will show us that if it is associated with the same author and with the same topic of discussion as "productive; zakat", then the number of documents found is still very limited, pay attention to the following table.

Table 3: The most dominant authors

Ranking	Author	Document	Quotation
1	(Widiastuti et al., 2018, 2021; Widiastuti & Rani, 2020)	3	8

It can be seen in table 3 that the author only produced 3 documents in the last 4 years. And in table 4 the following will be shown the number of citations of the article related to "productive; zakat" and the average number of quotes per year.

Table 4: Author and average citation

Citations	Author	year	GSRank	Citations Per Year
6	(Hariyanto et al., 2020)	2020	1	3
6	(Widiastuti et al., 2018)	2018	2	1.5
5	(Njoto-Feinard, 2014)	2014	3	0.63
5	(Baidhaw, 2015)	2015	4	0.71
2	(Mohsin et al., 2021)	2021	5	2
2	(Widiastuti et al., 2021)	2021	6	2
2	(Grace & Nurzaman, 2019)	2019	7	0.67
2	(Zaenal et al., 2018)	2018	8	0.5
1	(Ryandono & Nanda, 2020)	2020	9	0.5
1	(Calder, 2017)	2017	10	0.2
1	(Gantira Mira et al., 2020)	2020	11	0.5
1	(Rini et al., 2020)	2020	12	0.5
1	(Sumai et al., 2019)	2019	13	0.33
1	(Adnan et al., 2019)	2019	14	0.33
1	(Princess et al., 2019)	2019	15	0.33

After the data seen in table 4 is described in general with the average citations per year, then in table 5 the following shows how the description of the quotes related to "productive; zakat" when combined with articles published in Scopus indexed journals.

Table 5: Articles and number of citations

Citations	Author	Journal	GS Rank
6	(Hariyanto et al., 2020)	International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology	1
6	(Widiastuti et al., 2018)	Humanities and Social Sciences Reviews	2
5	(Njoto-Feinard, 2014)	Studies Islamika	3
5	(Baidhawiy, 2015)	Al-Jami'ah	4
2	(Mohsin et al., 2021)	Economics, Law, and Institutions in Asia Pacific	5
2	(Widiastuti et al., 2021)	Cogent Business and Management	6
2	(Grace & Nurzaman, 2019)	International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management	7
2	(Zaenal et al., 2018)	IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science	8
1	(Ryandono & Nanda, 2020)	Journal of Economic Cooperation and Development	9
1	(Calder, 2017)	The Development of Islamic Ritual	10
1	(Gantira Mira et al., 2020)	IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering	11
1	(Rini et al., 2020)	International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change	12
1	(Sumai et al., 2019)	IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science	13
1	(Adnan et al., 2019)	Humanities and Social Sciences Reviews	14
1	(Princess et al., 2019)	Humanities and Social Sciences Reviews	15

Table 5 shows that the most dominant journals are the International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology with six citations and the Humanities and Social Sciences Reviews with six citations. Then table 6 below shows the average number of documents per year cited by various researchers.

Figure 2: Visualization "productive; zakat" with VOSviewer in the time span 2014-2022

In figure 2, it can be seen that in the period from 2014-2022 there were 26 researchers who studied “productive; zakat” and the mapping results also show that researchers do not conduct their research together or also cite each other's related article sources (co-citation) so that the mapping arrows are usually appears to associate between researchers one to another is not formed. Based on the colors displayed, it also shows that in the last 8 years (2014 and 2022) the dominant research team published articles related to productive zakat in Scopus only (Widiastuti et al., 2018, 2021; Widiastuti & Rani, 2020) with a total of 3 documents and 8 citations.

Table 6: Average quotes per year

Citations	Citations Per Year	Year	GSRank	Type	Journal
6	3	2020	1	Article	International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology
6	1.5	2018	2	Article	Humanities and Social Sciences Reviews
5	0.63	2014	3	Article	Studies Islamika
5	0.71	2015	4	Article	Al-Jami'ah
2	2	2021	5	Book Chapter	Economics, Law, and Institutions in Asia Pacific
2	2	2021	6	Article	Cogent Business and Management
2	0.67	2019	7	Article	International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management
2	0.5	2018	8	Conference Paper	IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science
1	0.5	2020	9	Article	Journal of Economic Cooperation and Development
1	0.2	2017	10	Book Chapter	The Development of Islamic Ritual
1	0.5	2020	11	Conference Paper	IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering
1	0.5	2020	12	Article	International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change
1	0.33	2019	13	Conference Paper	IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science
1	0.33	2019	14	Article	Humanities and Social Sciences Reviews
1	0.33	2019	15	Article	Humanities and Social Sciences Reviews

Based on table 6 citations per year the highest is 3 (three) in 2020 which is cited in one year, and the second highest is 1.5 quotes on average annually in 2018. In the first place, it was published in the journal International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology and the second rank of Humanities and Social Sciences Reviews with the total number of citations per year is 4.5 citations. Thus, it still needs to be developed and republished through the journal attached to table 6, because considering that there are still very few publication articles related to zakat productive in the journal.

If reviewed based on the country that publishes the article with the keyword "productive; zakat", then attached tabulated data in table 7 below.

Table 7: The Big Four Quotes and Country of Origin

Citations	GS Rank	Country	Institution
6	1	Indonesian	IAIN Madura, East Java, Indonesia
6	2	Indonesia and Malaysia	Airlangga University, Surabaya and Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka
5	3	Indonesian	UIN Jakarta
5	4	Pakistan, Japan, China	Mohammad Ali Jinnah University, Air University of Islamabad, Tokai University dan Jiangsu University

Based on table 7, it is shown that the most citations, namely six quotes, are from Indonesia and Malaysia and in the next ranking with one citation also coming from Pakistan, Japan and China. Furthermore, table 8 will be reviewed the number of citations with the origin of the institution and the country of origin.

Furthermore, if viewed from the origin of the country that is cross-tabulated with the number of citations, it will be presented as follows.

Table 8: The most dominant countries

Citations Per Year	Citations	GS Rank	Country
3	6	1	Indonesian
1.5	6	2	Indonesia and Malaysia
0.63	5	3	Indonesian
0.71	5	4	Pakistan, Japan, China

Table 8 shows that the most dominant countries are Indonesia and Malaysia with a total of 4.5 quotes on average per year. Then all data related to productive zakat that has been compiled (bibliometrically) using Harzing Publish or Perish is visually mapped using software VOSviewer.

Conclusion

In a structured and systematic manner, this research re-maps and analyzes various sources and literature that study productive zakat. The findings showed that it turned out to be a variable with the keyword "productive; zakat" and studies related to productive zakat are still minimal and rarely studied in the last 10 years. Data shows that from 2012 and 2022 there were only 28 studies that examined productive zakat in Scopus indexed journals. From these results it can be concluded and recommended that henceforth in future research, re-research can be carried out to analyze the variables of productive zakat in the field of shari'a accounting. This variable is also very likely to be published in Scopus indexed journals, because only 28

articles have only been published in a period of time the last 10 years. Other specific studies to be studied can be in the form of shari'a management and shari'a financial management taking into account the results of these very limited findings.

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